

8T – The Commutativity of the Coupling Constants Series

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation from an angle of commutativity, it is possible to reason for unbound matter. The commutativity is due to the overall sum of the coupling term to be order invariant. Up to this day we always analyzed according to original derivation, which is net curvature unbound, i.e. bosonic fields.

Introduction

First, we can represent the original equation, which regard Bosonic fields to be net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold. Those Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers or one - $\mathbb{P} \cup (+1)$, and propagating from matter clusters destabilized by the majestic (3), which is the electron, from the second element and above.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.21)$$

For each term from the second and above, i.e. the weak interaction:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

There is a symmetry we can impose on those terms, that is by changing the order of the elements. Changing the order of the elements makes no difference to the overall value of the coupling. The series in equation (1.21) will still hold either way.

$$\left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \left[\frac{1}{2}\right] + 2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow [3] + (3) + (8 * 3)$$

Now its matter clusters unbound due to the net curvature, which is the first in order. The point is not the physical meaning of such an event, but rather the commutativity of the primordial equation. If we take the final values of each coupling as the main objective, that the equation is order invariant, or commutative. The same applies for each higher element and lower as well in the coupling term. Another point regarding the strong interaction is that, it implies that the gluons are unbound. They must come from somewhere and as they are net curvature on the manifold isomorphic to one, each gluon pulls or increase the probability of arrival to other gluons. The same applies to each boson in each coupling term. For example the photon:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.3)$$

Suppose you had a set of K gluons bounded to a Quark Triplet, in that sense it does not matter in which order they clustered to the sea of gluons. We can vary the set as much we would like order wise. Therefore, from that angle there is a symmetry there as well.

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^{i=K} g_i \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^{i=K} (+1)_i \quad (1.4)$$

Of course, that the main representation in which bosons are propagating from fermion clusters with spin one- half is the most reasonable and seemingly best way to understand nature. This short assay does not indicate that the opposite is correct, but rather present the coupling constants series from viewpoint of symmetry, order invariance or commutativity.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is a Short Range Interaction" In: (2021)
- [4] O. Manor. "Light is Gravity" In: (2021)